

DIAGNOSTIC OF URBAN FLOODING AND LIVABILITY IN GHANA

Report 2025

SEPTEMBER 22nd, 2025

Organization: ITC-BMS, University of Twente

Delivered by: SPACE4ALL

Edited by: Florencio Campomanes V &

Lorraine Trento Oliveira

Funded by: Dutch Research Council (NWO)

**UNIVERSITY
OF TWENTE.**

Executive Summary

This report, produced by the Space4All project, explores the intersection on urban flooding and livability in Accra and Tema, Ghana – two rapidly expanding cities facing effects from climate change, unplanned urbanization and inadequate infrastructure. Despite reports and media coverage about the living conditions of the residents, especially those living in deprived settlements, spatial evidence at the city scale is absent.

Flood exposure analysis shows that while Accra has a larger total flood-prone area, Tema is more severely affected in relative terms, especially at hazardous depths above 50 cm. Overall, about one-third of the flooded areas in both cities are built-up, with deprived communities disproportionately exposed—59% of exposed deprived areas in Accra and 26% in Tema. At the same time, livability patterns reveal that most at-risk communities are also those with the lowest quality of living. The overlap between flood hotspots and low-livability clusters shows how vulnerabilities compound: poor infrastructure, exposure to flooding, and low livability reinforce each other.

The core strength of the project lies in its participatory approach. Residents of deprived urban areas (DUAs) are actively engaged throughout the process with local workshops, transect walk activities and mapping surveys. City actors – government representatives, NGOs and academia were also engaged in multi-stakeholder workshops. Participatory activities confirmed that flood models often underestimate risk in deprived neighborhoods, particularly in Tema, where tidal surges, clogged drains, and artificial flooding exacerbate impacts.

Ultimately, the results show that flood exposure is likely higher on the ground, underscoring an urgent need for targeted infrastructure and risk reduction strategies. With citizen science at the heart, our approach advocates for more livable and safer cities for all.

Contents

Executive Summary	2
Contents	3
1 Introduction	4
Project Context	4
Project goals and contributions.....	6
Understanding risk.....	6
Understanding livability	7
2 Methodology	8
2.1. Stakeholders Engagement	8
2.2. Local Data Collection	10
2.3. Flood modelling.....	13
2.4. Livability modelling	15
2.5. Limitations	17
3 Key Findings	18
3.1. Flood Exposure	18
3.2. Perceived urban livability	23
4 Key Learnings	25
4.1. Flood Exposure	25
4.2. Perceived Urban Livability	26
5 Recommendations for Planning Agencies.....	27
6 Outlook.....	28
7 Acknowledgements.....	29

1 Introduction

In August 2024, the Space4All team conducted an intensive data collection and engagement in Ghana, working in close collaboration with local stakeholders - including residents from six deprived communities, local authorities, NGOs and academia - to examine challenges of flooding and livability in Accra and Tema. Both cities face the effects of unplanned urban growth, social disparities and recurring flood events. Additionally, mass eviction has contributed to increasing inequalities, underscoring the need for locally relevant, spatially grounded knowledge to inform inclusive and resilient urban planning.

Together with communities and institutional partners, the project produced two key outputs: a high-resolution flood model and a cutting-edge AI tool for livability mapping. The fieldwork created a space for dialogue about climate impacts and underlying vulnerability aspects of the deprived communities, shedding light into possible strategies to respond to their local realities.

Project Context

Accra and Tema, two coastal Ghanaian cities of the Greater Accra Metropolitan Area (5 million people), face many of the same challenges. Accra, the capital, has approximately 300,000 inhabitants, while Tema hosts almost 200,000 residents (Ghana Statistical Service, 2022). The cities face the wet season from April to October, during which floodwaters regularly overwhelm already strained housing, drainage and waste management systems. Despite improvements from the work of the Greater Accra Resilient and Integrated Development (GARID) Project, these impacts still fall the heaviest on the most deprived settlements, amplifying underlying vulnerabilities.

Despite their proximity and shared challenges, important differences remain. The population density of Accra is nearly 3 times higher than Tema, intensifying the pressures in the capital city. Another difference is that Accra benefits from comparatively more accessible urban documentation and government engagement, including clearer communication with the city authorities.

In the project, six deprived communities, three in each city, were selected for in-depth engagement (Opetekwei, Old Fadama, Accra New Town, Ashaiman-Zenu,

Ashaiman-Tulaku and Tema New Town). These areas were identified based on their deprivation patterns and exposure to yearly flood events. Unlike previous work, this project seeks to directly examine links between flood exposure and livability patterns. Although it is widely recognized that deprived communities often suffer the worst impacts, there remains a gap in spatially explicit analysis at both city and community scales.

Figure 1 – Old Fadama Community, August 27th 2024.

The struggle for social and economic space in the cities is deeply rooted in complex structural inequalities, shaped by political and socio-cultural factors derived from the colonial urban development. On the one hand, residents of deprived settlements defy the planning regulations, settling in hazardous zones, pushed by the lack of affordable

housing. On the other hand, local administrative systems lack institutional capacity and tools to ensure equitable infrastructure provision and just land governance, contributing to the displacement of low-income population. This double bind renders many residents as passive victims of flooding, while systematic neglect fosters spatial inequality, in terms of provision, hazard exposure and attention from the state.

In this report, we address these gaps by generating new spatial data and emphasizing local knowledge and participation. Our goal is to inform inclusive and equitable planning, particularly of underserved communities most affected by these challenges.

Figure 2 - Opetekwei junction, August 27th 2024.

Project goals and contributions

Based on the current challenges, this project aims:

- I. To engage local stakeholders in the research process.
- II. To map the flood hazard extent and exposure in Accra and Tema.
- III. To map local perceptions of urban livability in Accra and Tema.

Understanding risk

The concept of risk plays a central role in flood assessments, particularly in the context of climate changes impacts. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Sixth Assessment Report defines disaster risk as the potential for adverse consequences on lives, livelihoods, ecosystems, and infrastructure due to climate-related hazards. Disaster risk arises from the interplay between three components: hazard, exposure, and vulnerability.

Figure 3 - IPCC Disaster risk framework (Sixth Assessment Report).

A hazard is defined as the physical event or phenomenon that could potentially cause harm. In the case of urban flooding in Accra and Tema, there are three recognized flood types: riverine flooding from overflow of rivers into settlements, coastal flooding from storm surges and artificial localized floods from poor drainage and waste systems (WRI, 2011). Exposure refers to the presence of people, assets, or ecosystems in areas that are subject to hazards. In cities, formal and unplanned settlements located in flood-prone areas are especially exposed. Vulnerability is the predisposition of exposed elements to be adversely affected when impacted by hazards. Vulnerability is shaped by a range of factors, reflecting socio-economic, infrastructure and governance conditions that may exacerbate risks.

Measuring these concepts and analyzing their interaction with the human and environmental factors is not an easy task. It requires a lot of (spatial) information whose acquisition can also be a challenge. In this report, we focus on mapping the hazard (flood prone areas) and exposure (urban built-up structures in flood-prone areas), assessing the spatial patterns of floods and quantifying the exposed areas.

Understanding livability

Urban livability is a multifaceted concept that describes how well a city supports the well-being and quality of life of its residents. It goes beyond providing basic infrastructure to include factors like safety, environmental quality, social cohesion, cultural amenities, economic opportunities, and participatory governance (Leach et al., 2017).

Livability is dynamic and context-specific, meaning its interpretation varies across different cities, communities, and individuals. This inherent subjectivity challenges the effectiveness of typical top-down urban planning models. Therefore, urban planning decisions must consider the lived experiences of diverse communities, including those in deprived urban areas (DUAs). Accurately understanding these perspectives requires robust data and inclusive spatial mapping practices. Without these, the already unseen communities in DUAs continue to be marginalized. This report focuses on mapping livability (the least and the most livable places) across Accra and Tema based on the perspectives of city planners and DUA residents.

2 Methodology

The Space4All project follows a participatory data-driven approach (Figure 4). In the sub-sections below we will detail each of the dimensions of the project, these include: engagement of local stakeholders; state-of-the-art modelling processes to map urban flood exposure and livability; workshops for data collection and critical dialogue; participatory mapping training and surveys as local evidences to support advocacy of marginalized residents; transect walks to complement the quantitative methods ethnologically; and the dissemination of outputs and documentation back to local stakeholders.

Figure 4 - The Space4All research methodology diagram.

2.1. Stakeholders Engagement

Citizen science is the foundation of this project - the involvement of residents in the scientific process - including different types and groups of stakeholders to incorporate ensuring their information needs into the project. This brings a wider range of people into the research, with benefits diversity and inclusion, enhancing the understanding of the lived realities and their existing urban challenges.

The first task, therefore, was to connect and select a local co-coordinator to support the fieldwork activities, connecting the team to key stakeholders that can benefit from the project and assisting in logistics and cultural aspects. Table 1 summarizes the stakeholders involved in the engagement activities. At the city level, institutional and governmental actors were contacted to participate in local workshops. At the community level, residents from six communities were invited to participate in workshops, training for a mapping survey and the survey itself. Figure 5 illustrates the location of each community involved in the research process.

Table 1 - Stakeholders involved in the project.

Stakeholder Category	Stakeholders Involved	Activities
Community members	Invited residents from six neighborhoods, including Assembly and opinion leaders	Capacity training, Community-scale workshops, Participatory mapping
Civil Society Institutions	People’s Dialogue (SDInet), Smart Nature Freak Youth Foundation	City-scale workshop
Government Agencies	Accra Metropolitan Assembly (AMA), Greater Accra Resilient and Integrated Development (GARID)	City-scale workshop
Research Institutions	University of Ghana	City-scale workshop
Private organizations	Big Data Ghana	City-scale workshop

Figure 5 - Study areas and selected communities.

2.2. Local Data Collection

The three primary data collection procedures during the fieldwork were: local workshops, capacity training, and field surveys. These procedures have different purposes: (1) in the workshops, participants mapped and assessed where flood events happen, collectively evaluated the results of the simulated flood map, and discussed and voted on their view of what a more livable area is in the city; (2) the training conducted with pairs of participants from each community instructed them to use the Google My Maps tool in their devices to map flood observation points from past rainfall events; (3) the field survey was conducted by the same participants, creating a reference flood data for model validation and for further use of the community.

Between August 14th and August 29th, a series of workshops was conducted in Accra and Tema. In total, seven - one in each deprived community and one at the city level. With the support of the local co-coordinators, 15 participants were selected in each workshop, with concerns of age, gender and community roles. At the city level, 15 participants were also invited, of which 13 attended, representing a series of institutional power and efforts in the city of Greater Accra.

The workshops were structured in three sessions: one focused on flood hazard model validation, the second on livability voting and the third on the direct and indirect impacts. The first session was a group activity. Using marker pens, pins and sticky notes, the participants marked areas that were correctly assigned as (recurrently) flooded and areas that should be marked as flooded and were not. They pinpointed previous flood events on the map, describing impacts on the neighborhoods. The groups presented their results in plenary and discussed validation procedures, indicating high agreement between them (Figure 6).

In the second session, the participants familiarized themselves with satellite imagery and with an online web interface. They were shown pairs of images from different areas across Accra and Tema and they would choose which one was a better place to live for them. After making these pairwise comparisons for an hour, we collectively discussed the reasons for choosing one area over the other. In the third session a methodology on vulnerability impacts in the city was explored, which

is part of a second stage of this project, thus further explanation is beyond the scope of this report and will be provided in further publications (2026).

Figure 6 - Workshops photographs in different locations across Accra and Tema.

On August 28th, the capacity training activity was conducted with 12 residents (two of each community) at the University of Ghana. The participants got familiar with the spatial content of Google My Maps and we conducted a participatory mapping tutorial adapted from the Data4HumanRights¹ material. The survey content was tailored during the tutorial, including information on flood event dates, depth and damage (Figure 7). Additionally, an online messaging group was set up to share information, address issues and provide feedback during field work. The surveyed data is stored in My Maps files (and permanently shared with the community members), while a copy was processed and used for quantitative model evaluation.

¹ <https://www.data4humanrights.net/training-materials/5-2-google-maps-app>

On September 5th, the 12 participants conducted a survey in their own communities and in the routes developed by them. No number of points or time limits were specified, letting the surveyors decide based on their level of satisfaction with their own work. The Whatsapp Group was used to report phone issues and when participants started and ended their survey.

Figure 7 - Left: Training activity in the University of Ghana. Right: Print screen of a surveyed point and respective table of attributes.

Additionally, a few days before the survey, we conducted a complementary ethnographic activity called transect walks with community leaders and members from Opetekwei and Old Fadama. The two communities were selected based on their consolidated state of development, different livelihoods (respectively, electronic landfill and fishery) and the fact that one went through some upgrading programs and the other did not. The route was approved together with them, considering security of the participants and the coverage of key flood spots and crossing points of the riverways. The goal was to explore the existing structures and conditions of the area. Following the map with a mobile device, the team observed (with photographs) flood depth markings, listened to the participants expressing their knowledge and identifying critical drainage areas, providing essential information on flood and livability factors for the communities. Figure 8 provides key photographs and shared insights from the transect walks about open sewage, bridge infrastructure and self-constructed drainage lines.

Diagnostic Of Urban Flooding and Livability in Ghana

Figure 8 - Photos taken during transect walks in Opetekwei and Old Fadama on August 27, 2024.

2.3. Flood modelling

This section describes the methodology of the flood mapping process. As the first step, a historical inspection was conducted, to verify past flood events reported in online media sources. An extensive accuracy check through the respective years was conducted, websites were screened, and official documents were collected to confirm the exact dates, duration of flood events and reported impacts. It became clear that most cases and provided data are reported mainly at the national level.

In the absence of flood information at city scale, the project drew upon a state-of-the-art flood model recently developed by the ITC Faculty researchers, FastFlood Simulation (FFS) application (Figure 9). This decision is based on (1) the low-cost and user-friendly aspects of the platform. The choice for this model reduced the impact of software costs and increased the future replicability of the method by the local stakeholders; (2) the lower computational demands, when compared to

traditional hydraulic models, allowing computation of large catchment areas in a few minutes.

The model requires input datasets representing rainfall events (duration and intensity), elevation, terrain and infiltration. Aside from rainfall, all datasets were automatically downloaded from the FFS inventory, using an open globally available repository. FFS allows for extensive calibration like other state-of-the-art flood models, but no calibration was conducted to reduce the computational complexity for prospective end-users and increase scalability potential.

Figure 9 - Interface of FastFlood App.

After simulations with each available dataset, the satellite-derived rainfall data was prioritized over open-access gauge measurements from the Trans-African Hydro-Meteorological Observatory (TAHMO)². The institute provided daily and hourly precipitation data for four stations in the Accra Region in a time series from January 2019 to January 2024. Among the four, the measurements of the Accra Academy School were the most comparable to the events reported on the Global Flood Monitor³. The 12-hour event on May 22, 2022, was selected for the final simulation due to the highest peak rainfall. Table 2 describes the selected datasets and the detailed documentation can be found on the official website⁴.

² <https://tahmo.org/>

³ [Global Flood Monitor](#)

⁴ [FastFlood | FastFlood website, free super-fast flood modelling tool.](#)

Table 2 - Input datasets.

Data	Source	Properties	Link
Rainfall	Trans-African Hydro-Meteorological Observatory (TAHMO)	Daily precipitation – no spatial resolution	https://tahmo.org/
Terrain	Copernicus GLO-30 DEM	Resolution: 40m	Earth Engine Catalog
Land use	Copernicus WorldCover	Resolution: 10m / 2021	ESA WorldCover 2021
Infiltration	SOILGRIDS (ISRIC)	Resolution: 250m / 2020	SoilGrids — global gridded soil information ISRIC

After fieldwork, the flood observation points collected using Google My Maps, were used to evaluate the performance of the model using a hit-and-miss evaluation. The non-numeric flood depth information (ankle, knee, waist and above-the-head level) collected by the community members was converted into numeric thresholds according to the table below (Table 3).

Table 3 – Categories of flood depth for quantitative evaluation of the flood model at community level.

Flood depth category	Ankle-height	Knee-height	Waist-height	Head-height
Numeric conversion	Up to 15 cm	Between 15 and 50 cm	Between 50 and 100cm	Above 100cm

After a quantitative localized assessment with the survey results, the flood hazard maps were overlaid with the Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) of 2025 to map and assess flood exposure in built-up areas. We used the following thresholds to categorize the different built-up categories: Low (up to 20% built up), Moderate (up to 50% built up), High (up to 100% built up). In the analysis, the degree of exposure changes depending on the density of built-up structures, that is, the denser an area is, the more exposed people and structures are, thus more at risk.

2.4. Livability modelling

This section describes the mapping of livability from different perspectives using artificial intelligence (AI). To produce livability maps from different perspectives, the pairwise comparison data from the DUA residents were separated from those of the city planners. The idea is that a separate AI model would be trained using the

⁵ Global Human Settlement - Download - European Commission (copernicus.eu)

livability preferences of the DUA residents and another of the city planners. These two models would then amplify the limited data that was collected to be able to conduct city-wide livability mapping.

Our AI model, also called AI-voter, had a structure that would take in two radar satellite images, specifically Sentinel-1, of two different areas and the corresponding collected vote as to which area is a better place to live (Figure 10). The AI-voter is trained to find patterns in the two images that make one of them a better place to live. With enough data, the models are then able to simulate selecting which of two areas is a better place to live as if they were either a DUA resident or a city planner.

Figure 10. Configuration of the AI-voter.

After training the DUA residents’ AI-voter and the city planners’ AI voter, thousands of images from randomly paired areas across the entire area were generated for each AI-voter to “vote” on. These “votes” were then used in a rating tool called TrueSkill which is typically used in online gaming. The idea is that each vote is a “game” in a tournament and as one image is chosen as the better place to live, it signifies a “win” in the tournament and its rating increases while the loser’s rating goes down. After several thousands of pairs (or games played), the final rating of each image is equivalent to its perceived livability.

The perceived livability maps from both perspectives were aggregated into hotspots, both positive and negative clusters of livability. These areas would be considered the most livable and least livable from each perspective. Finally, the areas of agreement and disagreement across perspectives of what was considered most livable and least livable were calculated and mapped.

2.5. Limitations

The flood exposure mapping methodology has a few limitations: (1) the data collectors using Google My Maps which can only map flood points along riverbanks and streets. It introduces a bias for validation; (2) many areas could not be reached, and therefore could not be measured during transect walks, mostly for physical and social barriers; (3) the number of flood observation points collected was not significant for a quantitative analysis, thus we did not include these points in this report; (4) the methodology applied in this project works with an absence of discharge measurements. It is possible that the results would be different if the local discharge behaviors could be analyzed. This would require local data collection campaigns to determine the base discharge conditions. Planning agencies should push integration of the slums into the formal urban fabric, including the residents into participatory mapping approaches and, consequently, in disaster risk policies.

The methods to develop the perceived livability results were limited by the following restrictions: (1) our data collection was limited due to time and budgetary constraints. We were only able to collect data from Accra city planners and not Tema as they did not respond to our invitation. We also were only able to go to three DUAs per city. Although our participants were relatively representative of age, gender, and location, there were still other DUAs that could have been included if more time and money had been available; (2) the subjectivity of the “a better place to live” makes it difficult to validate if a participant is making random choices or if that is actually their choice; (3) some participants had technical difficulties or were more indecisive than others leading to a low number of votes which could affect the performance of the trained AI-model leading to potentially inaccurate livability scores.

3 Key Findings

This section is split into two parts. As the flood and the livability models were conducted with different spatial resolutions, the findings are not aggregated in a single unit of analysis and present separate findings.

3.1. Flood Exposure

The results provide a comprehensive overview of flood patterns in Accra and Tema, including estimated flood depth and extent for the event of May 22nd, 2022. Figure 11 shows the spatial distribution of flood exposure of Accra and Tema, overlaid with the deprived (slum) areas.

In Accra, higher flood exposure is concentrated along the Odaw River in the western part of the city, where several informal settlements are located. These riverbank areas were originally designated as buffer zones, but the population migrating from within and outside Accra has increasingly settled there in the past decades. Some highly exposed pockets can be seen in the eastern of the city in more deprived areas like Teshie but also in more formal areas like Osu.

In Tema, flood exposure hotspots are scattered across the city, but highest exposure levels can be found in the Ashaiman district, right off the Ashaiman Dam. This district has dense population living in areas initially planned for agriculture, lacking infrastructure provision suitable for residential use. In Tema West, the areas around Odum Road and Nungua Road appear especially susceptible to floods, while in Tema Metropolitan, the area between the Sakimono Lagoon and the industrial hubs shows higher flood exposure.

Table 4 presents the statistical assessment of flooded areas. Considering both built-up and non-built-up areas, Accra, for its larger size, has a considerably larger flood prone territory when compared to Tema. However, when looking at relative proportions and more life-threatening flood depths (above 50cm), Tema is significantly more exposed. In relative numbers, Accra and Tema face similar relative exposure to floods, respectively 14% and 15% of the territory is prone to floods above 10cm. However, in absolute numbers, this accounts for 32km² of the Accra's territory and 15km² of the Tema's territory.

Flood Exposure

City Boundary DUAs Districts

Low Density Moderate Density High Density

Figure 11 - Flood Exposure Maps of Accra and Tema including the delineated deprived urban areas (DUAs).

Table 4 – Flood statistics of Accra and Tema (absolute and relative values) at different flood depths.

		Accra	Tema
Flood-prone Area (in km²)	Floods above 10cm	32km ²	15km ²
	Floods above 50cm	16km ²	9km ²
Percentage of flood-prone areas (%)	Floods above 10cm	14%	15%
	Floods above 50cm	8%	9%
Percentage of areas exposed to floods above 10cm (%)	High exposure	35%	10%
	Moderate exposure	45%	42%
	Low exposure	20%	48%

When focusing solely on built-up areas, this picture shifts. In Accra, the findings show that from the 32km² of exposed areas, 35% are high density areas and 45% moderate-density areas. In Tema, out of the 15km², 10% is highly dense and 42% is moderately dense. Given Accra’s overall density is about three times higher than Tema’s, the flood risks there are proportionally more severe.

At the intra-urban level, the most flood prone districts are Tema Metropolitan, Accra Metropolis, Ablekuma Central and Tema West, all of them with over 20% of their area susceptible to floods above 10cm. However, exposure patterns differ when considering density (Figure 12). For example, Ayawaso Central has only 10% of its territory prone to floods, but 90% of that is high-density, exposing a larger number of structures and people to flood impacts. The presence of dense deprived settlements such as Accra New Town further compounds vulnerability and, thus, higher flood risk. Ayawaso North, Accra Metropolis and Ablekuma North comes in sequence with 63%, 59% and 53% of their flood-susceptible areas as highly exposed.

In absolute values, even though Tema districts do not seem highly exposed, in absolute values, the districts of Tema West and Tema Metropolitan have, respectively, 7km² and 6 km² exposed to floods, that is, the highest exposed areas between the two cities (Table 5). In Accra, the district of La Dade-Kotopon also presents a high absolute area exposed to floods, 5.5km², with over 60% moderately built-up in early-stage formal development near the Kpeshie Lagoon. This

demonstrates that both planned and unplanned areas are highly exposed to floods and require different mitigation strategies.

Figure 12 - Percentage of built-up areas exposed to floods per built-up density class in each district.

In comparing flood exposure in deprived and non-deprived areas, significant differences emerge. In Accra, we found that 26% of the non-deprived (formal) areas are densely built-up, against 59% of the deprived areas (Figure 11). This suggests that deprived communities – already more vulnerable – face disproportion high flood exposure. In Tema, even though with smaller relative values, the comparison is dramatic. While only 4% of the exposed non-deprived areas are densely built-up, 26% of the exposed deprived areas are highly built up. This indicates over ¼ of the deprived areas are at high risk. As a secondary city, Tema receives less attention from research and governmental initiatives, which puts the exposed populations in worst conditions.

Table 5 - Total exposed area (square meters) at each density class. The total sum of exposed areas (excluding non-built-up areas) per district is provided in square kilometers.

District	Non Built-up	Low-Density	Medium-Density	High-Density	Total (km²)
<i>Ablekuma Central</i>	55000	377500	1175000	1480000	3.03
<i>Ablekuma North</i>	2500	245000	2265000	2787500	5.30
<i>Ablekuma West</i>	65000	505000	795000	715000	2.02
<i>Accra Metropolis</i>	10000	185000	325000	760000	1.27
<i>Ayawaso Central</i>	0	0	15000	142500	0.16
<i>Ayawaso East</i>	0	137500	187500	102500	0.43
<i>Ayawaso North</i>	0	107500	292500	670000	1.07
<i>Ayawaso West</i>	435000	1130000	1722500	910000	3.76
<i>Korle Klottey</i>	0	132500	470000	520000	1.12
<i>Krowor</i>	120000	307500	1327500	365000	2.00
<i>La Dade-kotopon</i>	542500	2037500	2695000	597500	5.33
<i>Ledzokuku</i>	90000	470000	1970000	597500	3.04
<i>Okaikwei North</i>	682500	505000	700000	1382500	2.59
<i>Tema Metropolitan</i>	5290000	2525000	2455000	447500	5.43
<i>Tema West Municipal</i>	2950000	3637500	2812500	447500	6.90
<i>Tema-Ashaiman</i>	880000	1000000	1075000	560000	2.64

When we look closely at the six selected deprived areas, the participatory activities conducted on site revealed important differences on the ground. During the workshops, the participants indicated underestimation trends of the model, in coastal areas – where the model cannot capture tidal surges – and spots of artificial floods. For example, residents of Zenu and Tulaku mapped many streets that flood regularly but appear as safe spots in the flood simulations. In contrast, the residents from Accra and the city planners mostly agreed with the simulation outputs. This suggests that the flood model most likely underestimates flood exposure in Tema, especially in deprived neighborhoods, as it cannot capture the complexity of localized flooded areas.

During the transect walks in Accra, we witnessed some mitigation measures from both the government and residents (Figure 8). A large-scale dredging work was underway in Old Fadama, which residents reported to occur on a yearly basis to reduce floods in the Korle Lagoon. In internal alleys, residents have been self-constructing roads and drainage lines, often raising road levels over time, forcing houses to sit progressively lower (thus more vulnerable to floods). In Mpoase, blocked gutters were widespread and stagnant waters persisted long after rainfall, contributing to water borne diseases – often caused by shallow floods. There,

residents have tried to protect homes and schools by laying rubber foundations and building stone barriers. These findings reinforce that localized flood drivers – especially drainage infrastructure- plays a major role in determining flood impacts and should be prioritized in mitigation plans.

3.2. Perceived urban livability

The next section shows the level of perceived urban livability in Accra and Tema based on the perspective of city planners and of DUA residents.

For city planners, livability scores were generally high (>0.5) across both Accra and Tema. However, specific areas known to be deprived like Old Fadama and Accra New Town in Accra and Zenu in Tema, had low livability scores. The highest livability scores were found in the central area between the urban centers of Accra and Tema. In the hotspot analysis, Old Fadama and Accra New Town were the largest clusters of low livability in Accra while it was Zenu for Tema.

Figure 13. Perceived urban livability score and hotspot maps of Accra and Tema.

For DUA residents, livability was perceived more evenly across the territory but still with several areas having low livability scores. For example, the coastal area near Opetekwei in Accra had low livability scores. The surrounding areas of the airport had high livability and like the city planners, Accra New Town also had low livability. The hotspot analysis revealed that the coastal area of Accra and Accra New Town had the largest clusters of low livability in Accra. Meanwhile, parts of Zenu and Tema New Town had clusters of low livability in Tema. The high livability clusters were the areas surrounding the airport.

Figure 14. Agreement and disagreement of livability hotspots between planners and DUA residents.

There were both convergences and divergences between the DUA residents’ and city planners’ perceived livability maps (Figure 14). In Accra, both considered livability in the dense urban area of Accra New Town as low (Figure 14-1). The livability in the coastal area of Opetekwei was found to be low only by the DUA residents (Figure 14-2) while the city planners perceived the livability in the dense urban area of Old Fadama along the Odaw river as low (Figure 14-3). In Tema, fewer areas were found to be low in general but there was some agreement between both perspectives that the livability in Community 1 and Tulaku was relatively low. Only the DUA residents considered livability in Tema New Town as low while livability in a newly developed area west of the Sakumono lagoon was also perceived as low.

4 Key Learnings

This report provides a foundation for informed decision-making and strategic planning to mitigate flood exposure and to enhance livability in Accra and Tema. The analysis reveals important insights:

4.1. Flood Exposure

- 1. Flood exposure is widespread but unevenly distributed.** Accra has a larger total area exposed to floods, but Tema shows proportionally higher exposure, especially at more dangerous flood depths exceeding 50cm height. At the same time, a third of the flood exposed areas are highly dense built-up areas in Accra, against only 10% in Tema.
- 2. Deprived settlements face disproportionate flood impacts.** Flood exposure is strongly concentrated in deprived, densely built-up areas. In Accra, almost 60% of flood-exposed deprived areas are high-density, compared to 26% in formal areas. In Tema, the gap is even starker: 26% of deprived areas are highly built-up, while only 4% of non-deprived areas are.
- 3. Local factors strongly influence flood exposure.** Many flood hotspots in Accra and Tema result from local conditions, named artificial flood factors, such as poor drainage, blocked gutters and unplanned development. As natural water flows are impeded by the unplanned urban layout, informal infrastructure and inadequate waste disposal, artificial floods increase the severity of impacts. These factors cannot be well captured by our models and suggest that the true extent of flood exposure on the ground is likely higher than reported here.
- 4. Participatory processes are essential for local understanding of flood vulnerability.** Involving the local communities has proven essential: residents spotted model inaccuracies, critically discussed the possible flood causes, shared adaptations measures. The communities are aware of the problems of building in riparian zones and are interested in contributing to mitigation and prevention measures. However, while these actions are resourceful, they are not substituted for coordinated investment in drainage, sanitation and flood management infrastructure.

4.2. Perceived Urban Livability

The perceived urban livability analysis uncovers several insights on how differing perspectives affect data that goes into urban planning:

1. **Livability is generally low in the main urban centers of both Accra and Tema while most high livability areas are found in the “transition zone” between both cities.** This shows how much urban density is an important factor in what locals, both DUA residents and city planners, consider as a “better place to live in”. Discussions during the workshops support this as “good ventilation” or space between homes often came up as must-haves in a good place to live.
2. **In terms of livability, city planners sometimes disagree with the DUA residents as to what each considers as low livability areas.** In Accra, city planners did not find the urban areas near the coast to be of lower livability, contrary to the perspectives of the DUA residents. City planners also found the dense urban area along the Odaw river as a low livability area, while the DUA residents did not. This, however, does not mean that the DUA residents found these areas as highly livable. The DUA residents also had low livability scores for dense areas near the river but not as low as the areas near the coast.
3. **There are agreements between DUA residents and city planners in where some low livability areas are located.** The dense area of Accra New Town was considered as a low livability area by both. Going back to the first point where urban density is an important factor in how locals perceive livability; Accra New Town is a large and highly dense area. Also, the relatively dense area of Tulaku had some level of agreement between the city planners and the DUA residents.
4. **Including the perspectives of marginalized groups like DUA residents is essential for equitable urban planning.** If city planners made urban planning decisions solely on datasets from their own perspective, for example the livability maps produced here, then areas like the coastal urban areas would be left out of development plans. This application of livability mapping is only one of many where certain decisions may be different if a more holistic and inclusive view was taken.

5 Recommendations for Planning Agencies

Resilient urban planning requires context-specific strategies, and for that urban projects need to ensure the engagement of community members. This should push new efforts (and resources) to integrate the most deprived communities into sustainable and resilient plans. We propose the following priorities for action:

6 Outlook

This project is specifically interested in the dissemination of the outputs to local stakeholders. There are many possibilities for knowledge transfer, including (1) the training of the institutional staff to work with FFS platform for rapid flood assessment; (2) dissemination of printed maps and infographics summarizing the results testified in this report; (3) the promotion of photo exhibition, supporting ongoing community awareness campaigns; (4) and outreach via media sources, such as dissemination videos.

In the next part of the research, we will focus on the relationships between flood impacts and underlying local vulnerabilities. This analysis was already initiated during the local workshops by the codesign of the impact chains. The project will continue to work with the local government and the local communities, offering support and collaborating for knowledge exchange and feedback. We will also work on how livability perspectives are similar or dissimilar with other cities from other African countries. In this way, different cities with seemingly similar livability perspectives may learn from each other.

This image was AI-generated.

7 Acknowledgements

We acknowledge and appreciate the support of the Dutch Research Council (NWO) for funding this project. We greatly thank the supervision team of the project, Dr. Monika Kuffer, Dr. Mariana Belgiu and Dr. Anne M. Dijkstra for granting this work and trusting our capacities to conduct the Space4AI project (File number OCENW.M.21.168), entitled “Mapping climate vulnerabilities of slums by combining citizen science and earth observation technology”.

We utmost value the contributions of local government agencies, community organizations, and research institutions for their cooperation and valuable insights. Special thanks to our local co-anchors, Dr. Prosper Adiku and Mr. Philip Darko for their massive contribution to this project process. Your incredible feedback and support in the fieldwork activities shaped the results we got.

8 References list

Ghana Statistical Service. (2022). Ghana 2021 Population and Housing Census (General Report).

<https://census2021.statsghana.gov.gh/gssmain/fileUpload/reportthelist/Volume%203%20Highlights.pdf>

IPCC. Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Working Group II contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (Cambridge University Press, 2022). doi:10.1017/9781009325844

Leach, J. M., Lee, S. E., Hunt, D. V. L., & Rogers, C. D. F. (2017). Improving city-scale measures of livable sustainability: A study of urban measurement and assessment through application to the city of Birmingham, UK. *Cities*, 71, 80–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2017.06.016>

World Resource Institute (2011). Making Adaptation Count. Concepts and Options for Monitoring and Evaluation of Climate Change Adaptation. Eschborn: GIZ.

http://pdf.wri.org/making_adaptation_count.pdf

DIAGNOSTIC OF URBAN FLOODING AND LIVABILITY IN GHANA

FINAL REPORT

<https://www.itc.nl/space4all/>

UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE.

UNIVERSITY OF GHANA

GARID
GREATER ACCRA RESILIENT AND INTEGRATED DEVELOPMENT

ACCRA METROPOLITAN ASSEMBLY

